

Short Communication

Correlation Study of Temperature and Relative Humidity on the Growth of *Jatropha curcas* (Linn) Seedlings

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Abstract

The study was carried out to investigate the correlation between air temperature, relative humidity and the growth of *Jatropha curcas* seedlings. Sterilized river sand was used to raise the seedlings before being transplanted into polythene pots two weeks after germination. There were 42 polythene pots altogether, with pots arranged at an interval of 20m by 20m apart to enhance good aeration. Germinated seedlings were placed at the Agro-climatological station of the Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria (FRIN) for proper monitoring of climate effect. The climate parameter observed were temperature and relative humidity while the growth parameters of *Jatropha curcas* seedlings observed are stem height, stem diameter and leaf count. The experiment covered 15 weeks with 12 weeks of through observation, measurement and recording of data. Simple correlation coefficient (r) was used to determine the relationship between each of the climatic elements and the growth parameter of *Jatropha curcas* while the student t-test was used to test the significance of the relationship at 0.05 and 0.01 levels of significance. The mean of the measurement was used for the analysis. Results of the simple correlation coefficient (r) analysis revealed that there were a positive relationship between the relative humidity, temperature and the growth of *Jatropha curcas* with respect to stem height, stem diameter and leaf count. Further statistical analysis using student t-test showed that the relationship between the temperature and the growth of *Jatropha curcas* seedlings is insignificant at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance. On the other hand, there is a

significant positive relationship between the relative humidity and the growth of *Jatropha curcas* seedlings at 0.05 and 0.01 levels of significance. Finally, the study recommends that the temperature range between 30° C - 34° C and relative humidity (85-92%) should be used by the nursery workers, silviculturist and green house workers in raising *Jatropha curcas* seedlings in the green house. Besides, findings should be communicated to the stake holder's so that it can be used for predictive purposes so as to avoid future seedlings failure with the misleading or misunderstanding of the required climate condition for proper and maximum production of *Jatropha curcas* seedlings in the tropics.

Keywords: *Jatropha curcas*, silviculturist, relative humidity, FRIN

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Introduction

Ayoade (1988) revealed that climate and climate variability exerts a tremendous influence on plant growth and overall development. These, influence may be positive or negative. As a result of the negative impact, researchers often view climate primarily as a hazard and neglected it as a resource depending on time, location and the values and type of climatic parameters involved. However, Temperature and relative humidity are very important climatic component of the tropical environment and must be understood and taken into consideration in seedlings production.

Apart from the precipitation, temperature is probably the most talked about climatic elements (Ayoade, 2005). Regardless of how favorable light and moisture conditions may be, plant growth will be ceased when the temperature falls below a certain maximum value. There is optimum temperature at which growth proceeds with the greatest speed. Hence, every plant has an optimum temperature growth and upper and lower limit beyond which all growth stops. Besides, the optimum temperature for growth and the range over which it occurs varies widely from species and even between ecotypes of the same species. That is, the temperature for seedling establishment and growth varies between different organs of the same plant and even between two sides of the same region.

The temperature requirements of plant seedlings change as a plant age so that the apparent optimum may be varied according to the length of time over which the measurements are made. According to James (1977), relative humidity is of next importance to temperature and plays a major role in plant growth and development. It is a fraction of air temperature, wind, transpiration and evaporation from both the vegetation and the moisture of the surface layer of the soil. It is highly variable with

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respect to time of the day, season of the year and weather. In addition, different climatic element has the tendency of affecting different organ of the same plant in term of overall growth and development (James, 1977). As a result there is an urgent need to study the correlation between temperature and relative humidity on the growth of *Jatropha curcas* seedling.

Jatropha curcas locally known as igi “lapalapa” by the Yorubas, belong to the family Euphorbiaceae. It is a native of Central America and has become naturalized in many tropical areas including India, Africa and North America. It has great economic, medicinal and environmental benefit and has been considered one of the best candidates for the eradication of poverty among the rural dwellers. It grows anywhere, even on the gravely, sand and saline soils. It can thrive in the poorest stony soil; it can grow even in the crevices of rocks. The leaves shed during winter months form mulch around the base of the plant while the organic matter from shed leaves enhances earthworm activities in the soil around the root of the zone of the plants. This improves the soil fertility in the tropics and sub-tropics. Although it does well even in lower temperatures and can withstand a light frost, its water requirement is extremely low and it can stand periods of drought by shedding most of its leaves to reduce transpiration loss.

Jatropha curcas is also suitable for preventing soil erosion and shifting of sand dunes (Heller, 1996). The plant is undemanding soil type, require no tillage, grow well in low rainfall condition (require only about 200mm of rain to survive) and sensitive to ground frost that may occur in the cold season. Though, it has been apparent that the impact of climate variation are relevant to almost avenue of forest woodland research and programs, little or none has been carried out to study the correlation between the temperature, relative humidity and the growth of *Jatropha curcas* seedlings.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Site

The experiment was carried out in the Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria (FRIN) headquarters, Jericho, Ibadan. It is situated at Jericho hill under the Ibadan North West Local Government Area of Oyo State. The area lies between latitude 7° 26' N and longitude 3° 26' E. The climate of the area is tropically dominated by rainfall pattern range between 1400mm-1500mm. The average temperature is about 32.2° C and relative humidity is about 65% (forest Conservation / Meteorological Unit /FRIN).

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Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria is bounded by residential, commercial, industrial and Agriculture centers. Open space, water bodies, government acquisition, public and semi-public land use are noticed around the region. The eco-climate of the area is rainfall with two distinct seasons which are dry season (usually commencing from November - March) and the rainy season from April-October (FRIN Annual Meteorological: Report, 2008).

Method

Jatropha curcas seedlings were raised in a germination box, filled with sterilized river sand. Two weeks after germination, seedlings were transplanted into the polythene pots. These polythene pots (42) were then transplanted and placed at the Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria's Agro-climatological station for proper monitoring of the climatic effect. The initial reading of both the air temperature and relative humidity were taken immediately along side with that of growth parameters of *Jatropha curcas* seedlings. Subsequent readings of the growth parameter were taken on a weekly basis while that of climatic parameter taken on a daily basis. The weekly mean of the climatic reading was used to correlate with the mean growth parameters. The experiment covers sixteen (16) weeks with twelve (12) weeks of thorough observation, measurement and reading of both climatic parameters (air temperature and relative humidity) and growth parameter of *Jatropha curcas* (stem height, stem diameter and leaf count). Equal silvicultural treatment like watering and weeding were given to the seedling used.

Procurement of Material

Vernier caliper was collected from the physics laboratory of the Federal College of Forestry, Ibadan. 30cm measuring ruler, field notebook, pen, polythene pots were purchased from the market. The seeds of *Jatropha curcas* were purchased from Oke-Ogun in Atisbo Local Government Area of Oyo State. River sand used for the study was collected from the stream along Nursery A of the Federal College of Forestry, Ibadan. Thermometer and hygrometer used for observation of both temperature and relative humidity were already positioned in the FRIN Agro-climatological station.

Seed and Sand Pre-Treatment

Jatropha curcas seeds used were extracted carefully from its shell and sun dried while the river sand was sterilized

Parameter Assessed

The following seedlings growth and climatic parameters were assessed during the experiment at an interval of one week.

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1. Stem Height: Measurement was taken from the base to the apex of the plant using graduation ruler.
2. Stem Diameter: With the aid of vernier caliper, measurement was taken below the base of the seedling.
3. Leaf Count: Counting the number of the leaves of the seedlings.
4. Daily air Temperature: Taken by using a thermometer and recorded in field book.
5. Relative Humidity: Taken by the used of wet and bulb hygrometer.

Data Collection

Data were collected on stem height, stem diameter, leaf count, relative humidity and temperature. The initial readings of each of the parameters of assessment were taken immediately after transplanting into the polythene pots while subsequent reading taken on a weekly basis.

Data Analysis and Hypotheses Testing

Correlation coefficient was used to analyze the data obtained so as to determine the correlation (r) between the temperature, relative humidity and the growth parameters of *Jatropha curcas* seedling place at the agro-climatological station of Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria (FRIN). If r is positive, there is positive relationship and vice-versa. Also student t-test was used to test the Significant of the correlation.

Results and Discussion

The result shows that the correlation coefficient (r) between the air temperature and the stem height of *Jatropha curcas* seedling is positive (0.060) which indicate the existence of positive relationship between the air temperature and the stem height of the seedlings. Hence the alternative hypothesis which stated that there is a positive relationship between the stem height and temperature is accepted. The result is in conformity with Heller (1996) findings which stated that *Jatropha curcas* seedling grows almost anywhere and can thrive under any climate condition.

Table 1: Correlation coefficient between air temperature and the stem height of *Jatropha curcas* seedling

Week	Temp (X)	Height (Y)	X - X	Y - Y	(X-X) (Y-Y)	(X-X) ²	(Y-Y) ²
1	33.80	15.50	0.108	-1.617	-0.175	0.012	2.615
2	24.10	19.50	0.408	-0.617	-0.252	0.166	0.381
3	32.80	19.60	-0.892	-0.517	0.461	0.796	0.267
4	34.00	19.80	0.308	-0.317	-0.159	0.095	0.100
5	34.00	20.10	0.308	-0.017	-0.005	0.095	0.000
6	33.00	20.10	0.692	-0.017	-0.012	0.479	0.000
7	34.40	20.20	0.708	-0.083	0.059	0.501	0.007
8	33.70	20.40	0.008	-0.283	0.002	0.000	0.080
9	33.90	20.50	0.208	-0.383	0.080	0.043	0.147
10	33.50	20.70	0.192	-0.583	0.112	0.037	0.314
11	34.00	20.90	0.308	-0.783	0.241	0.095	0.613
12	33.10	21.10	-0.592	-0.983	-0.582	0.350	0.966

The result clearly show that the calculated value of t is 0.190 and the tabulated value is 2.228 (5% level of significance) and 1.812 (10% level of significance). Therefore, since the calculated value for t is less than the tabulated value at both 0.10 and 0.05 level of significance. Then the correlation though positive, was not significant as presented in Table 1.

The result shows that the correlation coefficient between the air temperature and the stem diameter of *Jatropha curcas* seedling is positive (0.085). This indicates the existence of positive relationship between the air temperature and the stem diameter of the seedling. Hence we accept the alternative hypothesis that there is a positive relationship between the air temperature and the stem diameter of *Jatropha curcas* seedlings. This result can be link to the fact that the experiment was carried out in a tropical climatic condition thereby confirming Haller (1996) findings that *Jatropha curcas* grows in tropic and can thrive in any tropical environment.

The result shows that the calculated value of t is 0.27 and the tabulated value at both 5% and 10% levels of significance are 2.228 and 1.812 respectively. Hence, since the calculated value for t is less than the tabulated value at both 0.10 and 0.05 levels of significance. Then the correlation was not significant.

The result shows that the correlation coefficient (r) between the air temperature and the leaf count of *Jatropha curcas* seedling is positive (0.072), indicating the existence of

positive relationship between the air temperature and the leaf count of the seedlings. Hence, the null Hypothesis is rejected while the alternative one which states that there is a positive relationship between the air temperature and the leaf count if accepted. This supports James (1977) findings that different organ of same plant respond at differently to temperature variability.

The result shows that the calculated value of t is 0.23 and the tabulated value at both 0.05 and 0.10 levels of significance are 2.228 and 1.812 respectively. Since the calculated value for t is less than the tabulated values observed at both 0.5 and 0.10 levels of significance, the correlation was not significant.

The result shows that the correlation coefficient (r) between the relative humidity and the stem height of *Jatropha curcas* seedling is positive. (0.622), indicating the existence of positive relationship between relative humidity and stem height of the seedlings. Hence we accept the alternative hypothesis that says, there is a positive relationship between relative humidity and the stem height of *Jatropha curcas* seedlings. The result however shows conformity with James (1977) findings that *Jatropha curcas* does well even in low temperature (i.e. High humidity) and can withstand high frost.

The result shows that the calculated value of t is 2.51 and the tabulated value at both 5% and 10% levels of significance are 2.228 and 1.812 respectively. However, since calculated t value is greater than the tabulated value observe at 5% and 10% levels of significance, then the correlation was significance.

The result shows that the correlation coefficient (r) between the relative humidity and the stem diameter of *Jatropha curcas* seedlings is positive (0.628). This indicate the existence of positive relationship between relative humidity and the stem diameter of the seedlings. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative states that there is a positive relationship between relative humidity and the stem diameter of *Jatropha curcas* seedlings is accepted. This agree with Heller (1996) findings that *Jatropha curcas* does well even in low temperature (i.e. High humidity) and can withstand high frost.

The result shows that the calculated value of t is 2.55 and the tabulated values at both 0.05 and 0.10 levels of significance one 2.228 and 1.812 respectively. However, Since the Calculated Observed at 5% and 10% levels of significance then the correlation was significant. The analysis shows that the correlation coefficient (r) between the relative humidity and leaf count of *Jatropha curcas* seedling is positive (0.559). This indicate the

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existence of positive relationship between relative humidity and the leaf count of the seedlings. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative states that there is a positive relationship between relative humidity and the leaf count of *Jatropha curcas* seedlings is accepted. This also shows conformity with Heller's (1996) findings that *Jatropha curcas* can thrive under any climatic condition and does well in high relative humidity.

The result shows that the calculated value of t is 2.134 and the tabulated values at both 0.05 and 0.10 levels of significance are 2.228 and 1.812 respectively. Since the calculated value is less than the tabulated value at 5% level of significance, there is no significant correlation. However, at 0.10 level of significance, the t -calculated is greater than the tabulated value. Hence, the correlation is significance at 0.01 of significances.

General Discussion

The difference in the value of r with respect to temperature; stem height (0.060), stem diameter (0.085), leaf count (0.072) can be linked to the fact that optimum temperature for seedling establishment and the growth varies between organ of the same plant and even ecotype of the same species.

Likewise the positive and the significant responds of growth parameter of *Jatropha curcas* seedling to relative humidity can be linked to Haller (1996) findings that state that *Jatropha curcas* does well with high humidity and can withstand high frost. Beside, *Jatropha curcas* is a native of colder region the plant from such region can survive better at high humidity.

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